

Preparation of Some Optically Active Cyclic Monoanilides of L-(+)-Glutamic Acid

K. A. Thakar and U. S. Pathak

Several optically active cyclic monoanilides¹ have been prepared from L-(+)-glutamic acid and different substituted anilines. The rotations of the mono- and di-anilides², previously prepared, have been compared. The optical rotations of cyclic monoanilides are more than those of the corresponding dianilides^{3,4}.

Procedure: (+)-Glutamic acid (0.05*M*; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 30.1^\circ$; *l*, 1; *c*, 1.0 in 6*N*-HCl); m.p. 209°) was added to the respective mono- and di-substituted anilines (0.05 *M*) and the mixture was heated for 8-15 hr. at 200-250°. The next day, the product was decomposed by water and sodium carbonate solution (10%). The anilide obtained was crystallised from water. Yields, m.p., and optical rotations are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Some optically active cyclic monoanilides of the type

No.	Formula.	Cyclic anilides from R.	% Yield.	M.P.	* $[\alpha]_D^{25}$.	Found.	Reqd.
1	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	29.5	148-49°	-40.05°	N : 12.38%	12.84%
2	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	<i>p</i> - ..	36.7	198°	-33.35°	N : 12.54	12.84
3	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	<i>m</i> -Anisidine	25.6	146-48°	-33.67°	N : 11.65	11.97
4	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	<i>p</i> - ..	21.4	211°	-20.19°	N : 11.69	11.97
5	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	21.0	128-30°	-32.21°	Cl : 14.78	14.88
6	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	<i>m</i> - ..	50.4	122°	-20.42	Cl : 14.54	14.88
7	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	<i>p</i> - ..	33.6	195°	-17.54°	Cl : 14.49	14.88
8	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	<i>o</i> -Phenetidine	40.3	125-27°	-40.27°	N : 10.90	11.29
9	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	<i>p</i> - ..	40.8	180°	-28.15°	N : 10.91	11.29
10	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	2,3-Dichloroaniline	29.4	210°	-30.60°	Cl : 25.41	25.73
11	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	3,4- ..	29.8	150°	-18.18°	Cl : 25.51	25.73
12	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	2,4- ..	14.7	175-76°	-34.49°	Cl : 25.39	25.73
13	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	2,5- ..	14.9	168°	-30.80°	Cl : 25.49	25.73

* *l*=1; *c*=5 in acetone.

1. Gray, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1264.
2. Thakar and Pathak, *this Journal*, 1965, 42, 197.
3. Kauzmann *et al.*, *Chem. Rev.*, 1940, 26, 339.
4. Mislow *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 57, 1500.

TABLE II

Comparison of optical rotations $\{[\alpha]_D^{25}; l, 1\}$ between glutamic dianilides (diamides) and monoanilides (monoamides).

	CHCl ₃ .	Acetone.	EtAc.	MeAc.	Dioxane	MeOH.	EtOH.
1 (a)	-53.02°	-36.38°	-43.92°	-31.43°	-24.57°	+7.8°	+3.796°
(b)	-61.0128	-40.05	-49.93	-35.73	-28.67	..	16.890
2 (a)	-28.57	-14.50	..	-13.95	-12.95	+17.31	+12.50
(b)	-52.67	-33.35	..	-26.31	-19.12	..	+19.21
3 (a)	-33.30	-17.69	-30.31	-15.07	-11.16	+ 4.854	+ 9.55
(b)	-60.67	-33.67	-51.30	-29.94	-20.37	+ 8.61	+12.94
4 (a)	-23.42	-13.97	..	-12.59	- 4.03	+ 5.44	+10.74
(b)	-45.08	-20.18	..	-18.79	-10.34	..	..
5 (a)	-45.32	-26.28	-34.44	..	-13.37	..	..
(b)	-58.34	-32.21	-46.97	-40.06	-23.61	..	+14.45
6 (a)	-22.04	-13.18	-21.66	-14.68	-10.53	+ 6.44	+7.10
(b)	-33.91	-20.42	..	-29.03	-14.14	+10.94	12.75
7 (a)	..	-11.39	-16.25	-12.04	- 1.42	+15.25	+18.52
(b)	-30.23	-17.54	-24.81	-19.95	-11.40	+18.50	+20.67
8 (a)	-48.04	-34.22	-40.70	-30.12	-20.50	- 9.84	-13.04
(b)	-62.92	-40.27	-60.95	-47.60	-34.59	..	-28.66
9 (a)	-38.84	-21.63	-37.02	-23.81	-17.19	+ 5.26	..
(b)	-51.14	-28.15	-47.07	-32.43	-23.47	+11.62	+18.13
10 (a)	-25.87	-16.79	-22.04	-23.13	- 7.76	- 1.01	- 9.48
(b)	-37.54	-30.60	-37.42	-31.68	-14.62	..	-20.58
11 (a)	..	-14.79	-21.21	-21.49	- 6.58	+23.18	+ 4.62
(b)	..	-18.81	-29.13	-25.51	- 9.58	..	..
12 (a)	-47.37	-26.31	-28.74	-36.67	-10.67	..	- 4.26
(b)	-58.94	-34.49	-41.22	-40.12	-20.87	..	- 8.84
13 (a)	-36.77	-19.75	-22.86	-24.60	- 8	..	..
(b)	-48.01	-30.80	-39.19	-33.61	-16.00	..	..

N.B. (a) refers to dianilide and (b) to monoanilide.

The number corresponds to the anilides referred to in Table I.

The authors express their thanks to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for a J.R.F. for some period to one of them (U.S.P.) and also to the Gujarat University for research fellowship for the remaining period.